

SUPERSATURATION LIMITS OF SOLUTIONS. PART V.

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The work on the limits of supersaturation in aqueous solutions has been further extended. The results obtained confirm the previous observations that in most cases $T_s - T$ for any particular solute is almost independent of T_s . Further, preheating has been found to have very little effect on $T_s - T$ in solutions of cinnamic, fumaric and maleic acid. Unsaturated nature of these acids is assumed to be responsible for this behaviour.

In continuation with the previous work on the limits of supersaturation (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 183; 1944, 21, 103, 145; 1947, 24, 279) more substances have been studied. The experimental method is the same as given in the first paper of this series. In Tables I and II are recorded the results obtained.

In all the tables T_s denotes the saturation temperature, T , the temperature of spontaneous crystallisation, and $T_s - T$, the difference between the saturation temperature T_s and first T . Temperature figures marked with an asterisk signify that crystallisation did not occur down to this temperature. $S_w 100$ denotes the amount of substance in g. in 100 g. of water

TABLE I

Potassium thiocyanate.				Sodium chlorate.	
T_s .	T .	$T_s - T$.	T_s .	T .	$T_s - T$.
40°	32.0, 28.8, 26.5, 20.0	8.0 (?)	45°	23.*	
45°	31.2, 30.4, 19.4	13.8	50°	39.2, 34.6, 32.8	10.8
50°	38.8, 33.4, 18.3	13.2	55°	45.0, 35.0*, 30.0*	10.0
55°	42.0, 38.4, 36.2	13.0	60°	47.8, 47.2, 40.6	12.2
60°	46.0, 41.2, 37.8	14.0	65°	47.8, 26.8, 28.0*	17.4 (?)
65°	54.2, 52.2, 50.8, 48.2	10.8	70°	58.2, 44.4, 58.6, 45.2	11.8
			75°	61.2, 61.4, 65.2, 25.0	13.8
		Mean 13.0			Mean 12.0
Thiourea.				Ammonium nitrate.	
T_s .	T .	$T_s - T$.	T_s .	T .	$T_s - T$.
45°	33.0	12.0	40°	29.4, 29.0, 29.8	10.6
50°	37.8, 25.0*	11.2	45°	35.2, 33.0, 32.8	9.8
55°	43.8, 43.4, 38.0	11.2	50°	39.0, 39.2, 39.2, 38.8	11.0
60°	49.4, 49.2, 48.6, 43.8	10.6	55°	41.0, 44.8, 42.8, 42.0	11.0
65°	52.8, ...	12.2	60°	51.0, 50.8, 50.8, 51.4	9.4
70°	59.6, 59.8, 48.2	10.4	65°	53.2, 51.2, 52.8, 52.6	11.8
75°	61.8, 64.2, 58.2, 46.4	10.2	70°	62.0, 69.0, 57.6, 57.2	8.0
			75°	65.2, 64.0, 64.8, 65.0	9.8
		Mean 11.2			Mean 10.3

Ammonium oxalate**.				Benzoic acid.	
T_s	T	$T_s - T$	T_s	T	$T_s - T$
40°	28.8....	13.2	45°	28.0,25.0*	17.0
45°	32.4,30.2,26.0*	12.6	50°	32.2,30.0,26.0	17.8
50°	37.6,30.0*	12.4	55°	36.2,32.2,26.0*	18.8
55°	42.0,39.0,35.6	13.0	60°	43.0,42.2,36.0	17.0
60°	47.0,37.0,27.0	13.0	65°	47.2,44.6,46.4	17.8
65°	52.8,50.0,45.2	12.2	70°	52.4,50.2,51.0,46.0,46.0	17.6
70°	58.0,56.6,51.0,50.0	12.0	75°	57.4,57.8,56.8,53.6,52.6	17.6
75°	62.2,62.0,60.0,55.4	12.8	80°	62.2,63.0,60.2,54.0	17.8
80°	67.8,67.2,66.4	12.2			
	Mean 12.6			Mean 17.7	

Barium chloride.		
T_s	T	$T_s - T$
55°	30.0*	
60°	34.2,30.2,25.0*	25.8
65°	40.0,38.6,25.0*	25.0
70°	43.2,35.6,26.6*	26.8
75°	49.2,45.0,32.4*	25.8
80°	56.8,55.2,48.6	24.2
	Mean 25.6	

** Solubility of ammonium oxalate has been determined in this Department by Mr. M. R. Nayar. The values at various temperatures are :—

Temp. ...	40°	50°	60°	70°	80°
S_w 100 (g.)	10.0	13.19	16.96	21.9	27.37

TABLE II

1. Cinnamic acid.			2. Fumaric acid.	
S_w 100.	T	$T_s - T$	S_w 100.	T
0.10	43.8,43.0,.....,43.6		2.00	39.4,40.2,39.8
0.20	52.0,51.2,52.0,51.8		2.50	45.0,44.8,44.8
0.30	57.8,56.4,57.0,57.2		3.125	50.0,49.4,50.2
0.40	67.4,69.0,67.0,68.8		3.75	56.6,56.8,55.4,56.8
0.50	72.2,72.4,72.4,.....	17.0	4.375	60.0,60.0,60.4
at $T_s = 45°$	28.0,27.8,26.0		5.00	65.2,66.0,65.6
			5.625	68.4
3. Maleic acid.				
	S_w 100.	T		
	100	26.0		
	130	34.2,34.0,33.4		
	160	42.2,42.8,42.0		
	175	48.4,44.0,44.2		
	200	61.8,52.2,52.2		
	220	61.0,59.6,59.4		

As the solubilities of cinnamic, fumaric and maleic acids are not known, only the concentration of the solute in solution is given in Table II. In Table III are given the values of $T - T_s$, obtained from Table I and Table II (1), λ , the values of the heats of solution in cases where available, and the product $(T_s - T) \lambda$.

TABLE III

Substance.	λ (numerical values)	$T_s - T$	$(T_s - T) \lambda$
KCNS	6100 cal.	18.0	79300
NaClO ₃	5600	12.0	67200
NH ₄ NO ₃	6820	10.3	65016
BaCl ₂	6700	25.6	171520
CS (NH ₂) ₂	(?)	11.2	—
CO (NH ₂) ₂	3641	13.1**	47697
(NH ₄) ₂ C ₂ O ₄	11500	12.6	144900
C ₆ H ₅ .CO ₂ H	7690†	17.7	136113
Ph.CH : CH.CO ₂ H	7491†	17.0 (?)	127347

** See *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 183.

† Calculated from Williamson's equation (*Trans. Faraday. Soc.*, 1944, 40, 435) viz. :

$$\Delta H_{(Sol)} = RT^2 \left(\frac{dm}{dT} \right)_{Sat} \left[\left(\frac{d \ln f_2}{dm} \right)_{T_s} \left(\frac{1}{m} \right)_{Sat} \right]$$

valid for anhydrous non-electrolytes. As the solubility of these acids is very small, an approximation is made by putting the activity coefficient f_2 equal to unity. Hence the above equation simplifies to

$$\Delta H_{(Sol)} = RT^2 \left(\frac{dm}{dT} \right)_{Sat} \times \left(\frac{1}{m} \right)_{Sat}$$

The results given in Tables I, II and III show that $T_s - T$ for most of the solutes is, in general, fairly constant and almost independent of T_s , and further that the value of $(T_s - T) \lambda$ is round about 70,000 cal. for KCNS, NaClO₃ and NH₄NO₃.

It is a general phenomenon that prolonged and continuous heating helps to stabilise solutions against spontaneous crystallisation. A few notable exceptions to this general rule are the solutions of KI, KBr, KNO₃ and KClO₄ etc. as has been pointed out in earlier papers* and a probable explanation of this anomaly has been suggested in a recent communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 284) from this laboratory. The behaviour similar to that of KI, KBr and KNO₃ etc., has been noticed in the case of cinnamic, fumaric and maleic acids also. Whereas the effect of preheating is prominently displayed (Table I) by benzoic acid, ammonium oxalate and thiourea

*Even if stabilising effect does occur in these cases under very prolonged heating (cf. Jaffé, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 43, 565,) it is only very slight and is negligible in comparison to that in other cases.

A somewhat incorrect statement occurs in an earlier paper of mine (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 187; second para. line 5). The line should read "Jaffé (*loc. cit.*) has shown $T_s - T$ can be increased even in KNO₃ by intensive heating" and not 'intensive filtration' as was published. However, this does not in any way invalidate my previous statements as the difference among the various categories is quite distinct and marked.

etc., no appreciable heating effect is observable in the case of cinnamic acid. Like cinnamic acid, other water-soluble unsaturated acids may be expected to behave in the same manner. Spontaneous crystallisation of fumaric and maleic acid solutions shows clearly (Table II) that $T_s - T$ appears to be almost independent of the degree of heating.

A more detailed examination of the effect of preheating on solutions of these acids is summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV

S_w100 .	Cinnamic acid		Fumaric acid		Maleic acid*	
	T .	S_w100 .	T .	S_w100	T .	
0.20	50.8(2), 50.6(6), 50.4	2.5	44.2(2), 44.4(4), 44.2(10)	130.0	33.2(2)	
0.40	63.6(6), 63.8(6), 63.4(12)	3.75	59.4(2), 56.2(4), 59.0(6), 54.6(10)	150.0	40.0(2)	
0.60	68.6(6), 68.4(12), 68.6(16)	4.98	59.4(2), 60.0(4), 58.4(8)	175.0	45.2(2)	
		5.00	64.8(2), 64.2(4), 64.0(6), 62.8(12)	220.0	59.6(2)	

The heating in these experiments was performed after the experiments on crystallisation given in Table II were over. On comparing these cases with others e. g. benzoic acid, which inspite of its easy crystallisation from water has an appreciable heating effect, it appears that unsaturation of these acids has something to do with the small effect of heating on the values $T_s - T$. This is only a tentative suggestion in the absence of more data.

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* After six hours of heating some solid, insoluble substance appeared at the bottom of the sealed tube. Due to this, crystallisation started even earlier than the attainment of these temperatures.

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